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Decreasing Stem Growth in Common European Tree Species Despite Earlier Growth Onset

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ABSTRACT

Recent findings suggest that global warming is altering the timing of trees' phenological activities, including earlier emergence from winter dormancy. While early-season warming can boost carbon uptake, tree growth does not seem to benefit. The underlying mechanisms and the altered intra- and inter-annual growth dynamics, as well as their interaction with environmental factors, remain poorly understood. We analysed daily-resolved dendrometer data from 228 trees across 48 Swiss forest sites over 2012–2022 to examine stem radial growth timing, intra- and inter-annual dynamics, and environmental controls for five tree species. Our results showed that higher winter and spring temperatures induced an earlier accomplishment of annual growth—indicating earlier growth start—but did not increase the total annual growth in any of the species studied. In contrast, we found a significant negative growth trend for *P. abies*, *A. alba*, and *F. sylvatica* across a wide climatic gradient. The reduction in growth was associated with the decrease in the number of days with growth. The positive effect of higher temperatures in spring was canceled out by a negative effect towards the end of the growth period. Overall, such a negative effect of increased temperature at an annual scale was strongest in *P. sylvestris* and persisted over 2012–2022. The effect size of temperature was larger in explaining weekly growth compared to the effect sizes of precipitation or of soil water potential. This indicates that temperature, as an integrating indicator of growing conditions, can capture the variability of growth on a weekly time scale, which is less the case on a daily or hourly resolution. Overall, our results challenge the expectation that climate warming will offset carbon losses caused by heat and drought with a longer growing season. Our findings from five of the most common tree species in Central Europe do not support this assumption.

[Correction added on 26 September 2025, after first online publication: The copyright line was changed.]

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1 | Introduction

An unprecedented rate of climate warming associated with high vapor pressure deficit and extreme droughts has been recorded in recent decades (Dai 2012; Spinoni et al. 2014). These environmental changes have significantly altered forest phenology, including the timing, duration, rates, and cessation of growth (Estiarte and Peñuelas 2015; Fu et al. 2018; Grossiord et al. 2022), which have sparked research interest in understanding how phenological changes influence ecosystem processes and services (Noormets 2009; Tang et al. 2016; Arend et al. 2024). For example, how changes in phenology mediate tree growth and the overall ecosystem's net primary productivity (Liu et al. 2022; Dang et al. 2023), more specifically the changes in seasonal variation in albedo, partitioning of available energy, and vegetation-atmosphere exchange of carbon dioxide (Pielke et al. 1998). Therefore, it is essential to understand how and to what extent environmental drivers determine intra-annual tree growth and how the effect size of environmental drivers on tree growth has evolved over the past decades (Dow et al. 2022).

It is generally expected that warming will lengthen the growing season in boreal and temperate ecosystems, where winter temperatures limit metabolism (Euskirchen et al. 2006; Menzel et al. 2006), and that higher tree growth will simply result from more days available for carbon assimilation and biomass growth (Silva et al. 2016). However, Etzold et al. (2022) recently showed a non-linear relationship between the growing season length and the growth of seven temperate European tree species. In boreal and temperate regions, spring phenology is primarily regulated by temperature (Linkosalo et al. 2006). Cold winter temperatures are essential for dormancy release, while spring forcing at warmer temperatures triggers budburst and subsequent stem growth (Zeng et al. 2023). However, climate warming can reduce the accumulation of winter chilling, potentially counteracting the expected advancement of spring phenology despite warmer spring temperatures (Wang et al. 2020). Several studies have shown that early-season warming can cause earlier spring leaf-out and earlier onset of tree growth (Augspurger 2008; Lempereur et al. 2015; Zani et al. 2020). In contrast, late season warming associated with reduced precipitation can restrict tree growth to only the earlier part of the growing season (Gruber et al. 2010; Matula et al. 2023) or divide the growing season into two (Camarero et al. 2010; Tumajer et al. 2022; Salomón and Camarero 2024). Meanwhile, increased tree growth at the beginning of the growing season might be associated with an earlier cessation of tree growth driven by the seasonal build-up of water stress or radiation-induced leaf aging (Buermann et al. 2018; Eckes-Shephard et al. 2021). Understanding and quantifying these mechanisms may help to reduce uncertainties associated with forecasting and modeling forest productivity and global carbon cycling (Richardson et al. 2010; Keenan et al. 2014).

Temperature, relative humidity, soil water, and length of the day are physical constraints to tree growth (Köcher et al. 2012; Zweifel, Sterck, et al. 2021; Etzold et al. 2022). Rising temperatures can increase trees' water demand due to enhanced transpiration. As a result, warming-induced earlier leaf unfolding may lead to greater water use early in the season, potentially intensifying drought stress during the summer months (Dow

et al. 2022; Salomón and Camarero 2024). Depending on the environmental context, variations in the critical thresholds of environmental variables can enhance or slow down radial growth (Bose et al. 2020; Cabon et al. 2020; Peters et al. 2021). However, the patterns and magnitude of responses to environmental factors can also vary significantly across species because of contrasting physiological traits and functions (Chen et al. 2022; Etzold et al. 2022). For example, ring-porous species usually display earlier growth resumption and faster radial growth during the earlier part of the growing season than diffuse-porous tracheid-bearing species because the former species are required to produce large new vessel conduits each year (García-González et al. 2016). Moreover, species-specific differences in the onset and cessation of growth-related activities have also been observed (Martinez del Castillo et al. 2016; Etzold et al. 2022). These differences in time windows for growth can differently expose trees to environmental factors such as seasonal droughts and eventually affect the overall annual increment (Camarero et al. 2021; Etzold et al. 2022). For example, radial growth of ring-porous *Quercus robur* and *Q. petraea* in Europe was found to be more sensitive to spring droughts compared to winter and summer droughts (Bose et al. 2021). Meanwhile, the radial growth of the diffuse-porous species *Fagus sylvatica* was found to be more sensitive to early-summer drought (Vanhellemont et al. 2019). Among temperate European conifers, *Picea abies* has often been reported as a more sensitive species to spring or summer droughts than *Abies alba* (Vitali et al. 2018) or *Pinus sylvestris* (Aldea et al. 2022) due to shallower root systems and a stricter stomatal control of transpiration (Cocharad 1992; Zweifel et al. 2009; Peters et al. 2023). Thus, it is essential to understand how environmental factors influence tree growth at different phases of the growing season. Additionally, examining how the effect sizes of these factors vary among species can provide valuable insights into the mechanisms driving growth patterns (Rathgeber et al. 2016; Etzold et al. 2022). The results of such an analysis can help to predict how different tree species might respond to future environmental changes, enhancing our ability to manage forests sustainably and model ecosystem processes accurately (Tumajer et al. 2023; Martinez del Castillo et al. 2024).

In this study, we investigate stem radial growth timing, intra- and inter-annual dynamics, and environmental controls for five common temperate Central European tree species. Our research questions were: (i) Have trees been advancing their growth towards the earlier part of the growth season? If occurring at all, is that advancement related to warming in the previous winter and current spring, and do we have a trend in terms of early accomplishment of annual growth over the past 11 years, 2012 to 2022? and (ii) How does the relative importance of environmental drivers on intra-annual growth develop during the growth period and over the past 11 years, and how do those trends vary across species?

2 | Methods

2.1 | Study Sites and Species

We studied seven most common tree species in central Europe: Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), Norway spruce (*Picea abies* L. H. Karst), silver fir (*Abies alba* Mill.), European beech

(*Fagus sylvatica* L.), sessile oak (*Quercus petraea* Liebl.), downy oak (*Quercus pubescens* Willd.), and pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur* L.). We have grouped the three *Quercus* species together, as the number of sites for each species was insufficient to perform individual statistical analyses. We used 48 forest sites and 228 trees (i.e., 20 (7), 64 (22), 69 (20), 49 (15), and 26 (11) trees (sites) of *Abies alba*, *Fagus sylvatica*, *Picea abies*, *Pinus sylvestris*, and *Quercus species*, respectively, which are part of an extensive tree growth and drought monitoring network (www.treenet.info) in Switzerland (Zweifel, Sterck, et al. 2021). Geographic locations of the study sites are presented in Figure S1. In this network, radial stem growth is derived from measurements of stem radius changes of trees with high-precision point dendrometers (Zweifel, Etzold, et al. 2021) on mainly mature dominant trees (Table S1). The ranges of tree sizes (DBH and height), mean annual temperature (°C), mean annual precipitation sum (mm) and elevation of all study sites by species are presented in Table S1.

2.2 | Tree Growth Data

Tree radial growth was measured at about 1.3m above the ground (Zweifel et al. 2016) and the data was recorded and transmitted with Decentlab data transfer nodes (Decentlab GmbH, Duebendorf, Switzerland) with a logging resolution < 1 μm at every 5–10 min. The measurements were processed to a 10-min time aligned data set using the R-package “treenetproc”, including outlier removal, jump correction and linear interpolation of short gaps (Knüsel et al. 2021). Radial growth data, extracted with the zero-growth assumption (Zweifel et al. 2016) were aggregated on a daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly sum basis. As growth strongly varies within individual trees, across years, species, sites and climatic regions, annual growth was standardized by converting it to relative annual growth. This was done by calculating the difference between each tree’s annual growth to its tree-specific long-term average, calculated over the available data from 2012 to 2022. In this way, the growth response to changing environmental conditions is weighed equally for generally slow and fast-growing species and sites from different environmental conditions.

2.3 | Environmental Data

Air temperature (°C) data was obtained from weather stations (www.meteoswiss.admin.ch, mean distance: 8 km, max: 15 km) or were measured at the site and aggregated to daily values. Air temperature and relative humidity (%) at the sites were measured at 2 m height within the forest stands. Precipitation was extracted from MeteoSwiss model generated CombiPrecip (Maloku et al. 2024) combining data from weather stations and precipitation radar. The vapour pressure deficit (VPD, in kPa) was calculated using temperature and relative humidity following the procedure explained by Jones (1992) using the R package ‘plantecophys’ (Duursma 2015). Soil water potential (SWP) was measured with dielectric MPS-2/MPS-6 sensors (Decagon Devices, Pullman, US) at 10–20 cm soil depth at each site and the values were corrected for soil temperature fluctuations (Walthert and Schleppe 2018).

2.4 | Data Analyses and Statistics

All analyses, including statistical model runs and figures, were produced using the R statistical software (R Development Core Team 2022). For understanding the timing of growth occurrence, dates (day of the year) of four growth levels, that is, 5%, 25%, 50%, and 75% of annual growth, were defined for each tree. These growth levels were selected to assess the growth dynamics that occurred during the whole growth period and were adapted from Dow et al. (2022). The length of the growth period is the number of days between the starting day of growth and the ending day of growth. In addition, we measured the number of days with growth (daily growth rate > 0) within the growth period. The growth characteristics were calculated for each year separately. Species-specific linear mixed-effect models (Zuur et al. 2009; Pinheiro et al. 2014) were used to detect the effects of past winter temperature (average of December to February), current spring temperature (average of March to May), and decadal trends (2012–2022) on the four growth levels, relative stem growth, length of the growth period, and number of days with growth. Trees nested within sites were considered as random effect variables. We checked the assumptions of normality of the residuals and homogeneity of the variances for each response/dependent variable. The effect size of a predictor variable on a response variable was measured by the coefficient of the mixed-effect model.

For quantifying environmental factors controlling intra-annual growth, we modeled weekly growth as a function of day length, weekly temperature, precipitation, vapor pressure deficit, soil water potential, and interactions among those variables. We considered 16 candidate models for each species based on existing understanding related to environmental factors driving stem radial growth (Table S2). As temperature and VPD were highly correlated, they were not included in the same model. We considered different combinations of additive and interaction effects of predictor variables, and the best model was selected for each species based on the corrected Akaike Information Criteria (AICc) (Burnham and Anderson 2002). We used squared-root transformation of weekly growth to account for heteroscedasticity. The analyses were restricted to the species-specific growth period (Figure S2). The duration of the growth period for each species was taken from Etzold et al. (2022). Environmental variables were standardized to a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one to allow comparison of their effect sizes and to ensure that the contribution of each variable was not underestimated. The standardization was executed using the *scale* function of the *dplyr* R package. We used multi-model inference of the 16 models to compute the model-averaged estimates of the explanatory variables and their 95% confidence intervals (Burnham and Anderson 2002). A confidence interval excluding 0 indicated that explanatory variables of interest affected the response variable (Burnham and Anderson 2002; Mazerolle 2006). The coefficient of variation (R^2) for fixed and random effects (i.e., marginal and conditional) was calculated using the function *r.squaredGLMM* of the MuMIn package in R (Bartoń 2013).

To assess how the influence of environmental factors on weekly tree growth varies throughout the growth period, we quantified effect sizes using the coefficients from linear mixed-effects models fitted separately for each week. Each weekly model included

the fixed effects of the three most important variables—temperature, precipitation, and SWP—as identified through prior model selection. This weekly approach allowed us to capture intra-annual dynamics in the environmental control of tree radial growth.

$$\text{Growth}_{s,i,t} \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Temp}_{s,t} + \beta_2 \text{Precip}_{s,t} + \beta_3 \text{SWP}_{s,t} + \gamma_{0,s,i,t} + \gamma_{1,s,i,t} \quad (1)$$

where weekly growth of tree i of year t is nested within site s . $\text{Temp}_{s,t}$ is the weekly standardized temperature of year t of site s , $\text{Precip}_{s,t}$ is the weekly standardized precipitation of year t of site s , $\text{SWP}_{s,t}$ is the weekly standardized SWP of year t of site s , and random effects γ_0 and γ_1 are tree i nested within site s and year t .

For inter-annual dynamics of the effect sizes of those three most important environmental factors explaining weekly growth, we quantified effect sizes using the coefficients from linear mixed-effects models fitted separately for each year (2012–2022). Each yearly model included the fixed effects of standardized temperature, precipitation, and SWP. This yearly approach allowed us to capture inter-annual dynamics in the environmental control of tree radial growth.

$$\text{Growth}_{s,i,w} \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Temp}_{s,w} + \beta_2 \text{Precip}_{s,w} + \beta_3 \text{SWP}_{s,w} + \gamma_{0,s,i,w} + \gamma_{1,s,i,w} \quad (2)$$

where weekly growth of tree i of week w is nested within site s . $\text{Temp}_{s,w}$ is the weekly standardized temperature of week w of site s , $\text{Precip}_{s,w}$ is the weekly standardized precipitation of week w of site s , $\text{SWP}_{s,w}$ is the weekly standardized SWP of week w of site s , and random effects γ_0 and γ_1 are tree i nested within site s and week w . To understand the relationship between weekly growth and both the maximum daily growth rate (Chen et al. 2022) and growth sensitivity to the three key environmental factors (temperature, precipitation, and SWP), we calculated the Pearson correlation coefficient between these variables.

To explore the potential influence of tree age or size on annual growth trends, we analysed the growth patterns of ‘large’ and ‘small’ trees from two species, *F. sylvatica* and *P. abies*, separately. We selected these species because they had enough trees in both size categories across most sites. A site-specific classification of tree size (DBH—diameter at breast height) whether large or small was essential, as the size of dominant trees varied among sites due to environmental factors that affect maximum growth potential.

3 | Results

DOY (day of the year) at which specific stem radial growth levels (i.e., 5%, 25%, 50%, and 75%) were achieved was negatively related to past winter temperature, spring temperature, and decadal trends (2012–2022), but these relationships were not consistent across the five species examined in this study (Figure 1). Winter temperature was positively associated with earlier reaching of the defined growth levels of *F. sylvatica*, *P. abies*, *P. sylvestris*, and *Q. species*, while spring temperature was positively related to earlier reaching the growth levels of *F. sylvatica*, *P. abies*, and

Q. species (Figure 1). We also observed a linear trend over time resulting in an increasingly earlier reaching of growth levels over the period 2012–2022 in *A. alba*, *F. sylvatica*, *P. abies*, and *P. sylvestris* (Figure 1). When significant, the effect size of winter temperature at the DOY of radial stem growth levels of *F. sylvatica* decreased from 5% to 75%. This indicates that the control of winter temperature on radial growth declined towards the later part of the year (Figure S3). However, such a declining trend regarding the effect size of winter or spring temperatures was not clearly observable for other species (Figure S3).

Earlier growth start did not increase total annual growth. We detected a significant negative effect of an earlier start on annual growth for four out of five species considered in this study (Table 1). The length of the growth period and number of days with growth were positively related to annual growth for all species except *A. alba* for length of the growth period (Table 1). In fact, the total annual growth significantly decreased in *A. alba*, *F. sylvatica*, and *P. abies* (Figures 2 and 3) while the number of days with growth decreased for *P. abies* and *Q. species* over the past 11 years (Figure 3A). Although the length of growth period significantly increased for *A. alba* and *P. sylvestris*, the total annual growth or number of days with growth did not increase for either of those species (Figure 3A). The annual growth of *F. sylvatica* and *P. abies* showed no significant differences between large and small trees, with both size categories exhibiting negative growth trends over the past 11 years, although the negative trend was significant only for *Picea abies* (Figure S4).

Although winter or spring temperatures were positively related to the earlier onset of tree growth, they were unrelated to total annual growth except for *P. sylvestris* in response to spring temperature (Figure 3B,C). In fact, spring temperature was negatively associated with the number of days with growth with *Q. species* (Figure 3C). In addition to spring temperature, summer temperature was negatively associated with the number of growth days of *P. sylvestris* and *Q. species* (Figure 3D). Summer temperature was not related to total annual growth across the five species examined in this study (Figure 3D).

Annual radial growth responses to spring temperature and decadal trends were not related to the elevation of the site for none of the five studied species (Figure S5). Annual growth responses to spring temperature were not even positive (except few sites) towards high elevation sites, except the responses of *P. abies* at the uppermost site located in Davos at 1640m asl (Figure S5). Only six sites considered in this study showed positive responses to decadal trends, indicating either no trends or decreasing trends in radial growth over 11 years (2012–2022) irrespective of sites and species (Figure S5).

The positive effect of temperature with a negative effect of squared temperature indicates a quadratic effect of temperature on weekly growth during the growth period. Radial growth increased with temperature in the earlier part of the growth period (when temperatures were relatively low) but decreased with temperature towards the later part of the growth period (when temperatures were relatively high) (Figure 4). This pattern of response was consistent across five species we examined.

FIGURE 1 | Trees annual growth accomplishments are shifted earlier and are related to winter and spring temperatures. Dates of accomplishments of stem growth levels (5%, 25%, 50%, and 75%) were modeled as a function of (A) past winter temperature, (B) spring temperature, and (C) measurement year. Thicker lines indicate statistically significant trends ($p < 0.05$). ABAL, *Abies alba*; FASY, *Fagus sylvatica*; PCAB, *Picea abies*; PISY, *Pinus sylvestris*; QUSP, *Quercus species*. Shaded areas around the line indicate the mean \pm standard error.

TABLE 1 | Results of linear regressions used to test the effects of starting day of growth, ending day of growth, length of growth period, and number of days of growth on relative annual growth (relative to long-term average growth). *Quercus* species: *Q. petraea*, *Q. pubescens*, and *Q. robur*.

Parameters	<i>Abies alba</i>		<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>		<i>Picea abies</i>		<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>		<i>Quercus species</i>	
	Estimate ± SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate ± SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate ± SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate ± SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate ± SE	<i>p</i>
Starting day of growth	-0.0013 ± 0.0012	0.273	-0.0025 ± 0.0006	0.000	-0.0022 ± 0.0006	0.000	-0.0006 ± 0.0002	0.009	-0.0020 ± 0.0005	0.000
Ending day of growth	0.0016 ± 0.0013	0.241	0.0019 ± 0.0007	0.006	0.0020 ± 0.0006	0.001	0.0003 ± 0.0002	0.120	0.0006 ± 0.0004	0.102
Length of growth period	0.0012 ± 0.0008	0.142	0.0023 ± 0.0005	0.000	0.0019 ± 0.0004	0.000	0.0005 ± 0.0002	0.002	0.0010 ± 0.0003	0.000
Number of days of growth	0.0092 ± 0.0015	0.000	0.0093 ± 0.0009	0.000	0.0131 ± 0.0008	0.000	0.0062 ± 0.0006	0.000	0.0061 ± 0.0007	0.000

Note: Bold values indicate statistically significant results.

FIGURE 2 | Decadal trends of relative stem growth (relative to long-term average) from 2012 to 2022. Thicker lines indicate species associated with statistically significant negative growth trends ($p < 0.05$). Shaded areas represent mean ± standard error. ABAL, *Abies alba*; FASY, *Fagus sylvatica*; PCAB, *Picea abies*; PISY, *Pinus sylvestris*; QUSP, *Quercus species*. Shaded areas around the line indicate the mean ± standard error.

The positive effect of temperature stayed longer for the growth of *F. sylvatica* from the 17th to 27th week, but the positive effect switched to negative after the 23rd week for *P. abies* and *P. sylvestris* (Figure 4). Precipitation had a consistent positive effect (with few exceptions) throughout the growth period across all species. However, the effect size of precipitation generally decreased towards the later part of the growth period (Figure 4). The effect of SWP in the topsoil was often non-significant on weekly radial growth, where the effect sizes peaked towards the middle of the growth period and declined later. This pattern was consistent across all species (Figure 4). The effect size of weekly temperature on weekly growth was larger compared to effect sizes of other variables irrespective of species (Table 2). The model that included the effects of day length, temperature, squared temperature, precipitation, and SWP had the highest support (Akaike weight 0.77–1.00) for *A. alba*, *F. sylvatica*, *P. abies*, and *P. sylvestris*. In contrast, the model that included the interaction effects between day length and temperature and between day length and precipitation and the additive effects of squared temperature had the highest support of Akaike weight for *Q. species* (Table S3). Random effect variables (i.e., trees nested within sites) explained a higher percentage of variability than fixed effect variables, indicating the importance of tree-to-tree response variability within a site (Table S3).

We observed similar intra-annual trends between total weekly radial growth and maximum daily growth rate (MGr) that occurred within a week across five species (Figure 5). However, intra-annual weekly growth and weekly growth sensitivity to temperature, precipitation, and SWP varied across species. The relationship between weekly growth and growth sensitivity to SWP was stronger for *A. alba*, *F. sylvatica*, *P. abies*, and *P. sylvestris* compared to the relationship between weekly growth and growth sensitivity to temperature or precipitation (Figure 5).

FIGURE 3 | Annual growth decreased over the past 11-year period (2012–2022) for ABAL, FASY, and PCAB. The effect size (coefficient of linear mixed-effects models) of (A) decadal trend, (B) past winter temperature, (C) spring temperature, and (D) summer temperature in explaining relative annual growth, length of growth period, and number of days with growth. The error bars indicate the mean \pm standard error. ABAL, *Abies alba*; FASY, *Fagus sylvatica*; PCAB, *Picea abies*; PISY, *Pinus sylvestris*; QUSP, *Quercus species*.

FIGURE 4 | Weekly development of environmental control on tree radial growth during the growth period. Environmental control on tree radial growth was measured by the coefficient of linear mixed-effect models that incorporate the effects of weekly precipitation, SWP (water potential in the topsoil) and air temperature. The analyses were performed separately for each of the weeks and five species. The error bars indicate the mean \pm standard error.

TABLE 2 | Model average estimates with 95% confidence intervals (CI) based on model averaging for weekly stem growth.

Parameters	<i>Abies alba</i>			<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>			<i>Picea abies</i>			<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>			<i>Quercus species</i>		
	Estimate (β)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	Estimate (β)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	Estimate (β)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	Estimate (β)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	Estimate (β)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI
Day length	0.003	0.002	0.005	0.009	0.008	0.010	0.012	0.010	0.013	0.008	0.006	0.009	-0.003	-0.004	-0.002
Temp	0.106	0.084	0.128	0.107	0.093	0.121	0.126	0.113	0.139	0.037	0.018	0.055	0.090	0.071	0.109
Temp ²	-0.077	-0.089	-0.064	-0.040	-0.047	-0.033	-0.078	-0.086	-0.071	-0.040	-0.049	-0.032	-0.066	-0.083	-0.049
Precip	0.033	0.027	0.038	0.017	0.014	0.020	0.059	0.055	0.062	0.048	0.044	0.052	0.054	0.050	0.059
VPD	-0.028	-0.036	-0.019	0.014	0.010	0.018	-0.020	-0.025	-0.014	-0.024	-0.029	-0.020	-0.012	-0.017	-0.007
SWP	0.053	0.028	0.077	0.078	0.071	0.084	0.017	0.010	0.023	0.019	0.015	0.023	0.014	0.008	0.019
Daylength: Temp	—	—	—	0.004	0.002	0.006	—	—	—	-0.009	-0.011	-0.006	0.005	0.003	0.007
Daylength: Precip	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.002	0.0004	0.003
Daylength: VPD	—	—	—	-0.003	-0.004	-0.002	—	—	—	-0.002	-0.004	-0.001	-0.002	-0.003	-0.002
Daylength: SWP	—	—	—	0.004	0.002	0.006	0.002	0.0004	0.004	0.002	0.0004	0.003	-0.003	-0.005	-0.001

Note: A 95% confidence interval excluding 0 indicates a significant effect. Temp² = squared term used for non-linearity. “—” indicates the variable has no effect. The list of models considered in this study presented in Table S2. *Quercus species*: *Q. petraea*, *Q. pubescens*, and *Q. robur*. Abbreviations: Precip, Precipitation; SWP, soil water potential; Temp, Temperature; VPD, vapor pressure deficit.

FIGURE 5 | Intra-annual weekly trends are shown for total weekly growth, the maximum daily growth rate (MGr) within each week, and the coefficients of temperature, precipitation, and topsoil soil water potential (SWP) that explain weekly growth. These coefficients were derived from linear mixed-effects models. Pearson correlation coefficients between total weekly growth and each of the four other variables are displayed in each panel, with corresponding colors indicating the degree of synchrony between weekly growth and MGr and between weekly growth and growth sensitivity to temperature, precipitation, and topsoil SWP.

However, for *Q. species*, the relationship between weekly growth and growth sensitivity to temperature was stronger compared to the relationship between weekly growth and growth sensitivity to precipitation or SWP (Figure 5).

The trend of effect sizes of temperature from 2012 to 2022 was negative for *A. alba*, *P. abies*, and *P. sylvestris* (Figure 6). In addition, we observed negative effects of temperature on three coniferous species during the extremely hot years of 2018 and 2022 (Figure 6),

FIGURE 6 | Yearly development of weekly environmental control on weekly tree radial growth. Environmental control on tree radial growth was measured by the coefficient of linear mixed-effect models that incorporate the effects of weekly precipitation, SWP (water potential in the topsoil) and air temperature. The analyses were performed separately for each of the years and five species. The error bars indicate the mean \pm standard error.

TABLE 3 | Species-specific total number of days with growth (mean \pm standard error) for each study year from 2012 to 2022. *Quercus* species: *Q. petraea*, *Q. pubescens*, and *Q. robur*.

Years	<i>Abies alba</i>	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	<i>Picea abies</i>	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	<i>Quercus species</i>
2012	107 \pm 17	105 \pm 15	67 \pm 13	54 \pm 23	70 \pm 35
2013	105 \pm 15	113 \pm 13	82 \pm 10	27 \pm 17	97 \pm 22
2014	97 \pm 22	113 \pm 10	83 \pm 13	49 \pm 7	82 \pm 15
2015	116 \pm 19	112 \pm 8	61 \pm 8	56 \pm 13	66 \pm 13
2016	101 \pm 25	107 \pm 9	74 \pm 8	51 \pm 9	77 \pm 11
2017	96 \pm 27	81 \pm 11	55 \pm 8	39 \pm 8	53 \pm 11
2018	96 \pm 17	102 \pm 8	51 \pm 6	42 \pm 6	64 \pm 9
2019	93 \pm 20	107 \pm 10	53 \pm 8	51 \pm 7	62 \pm 14
2020	91 \pm 17	108 \pm 9	52 \pm 9	45 \pm 7	72 \pm 14
2021	111 \pm 19	112 \pm 10	60 \pm 9	54 \pm 7	71 \pm 12
2022	109 \pm 13	104 \pm 9	56 \pm 8	42 \pm 6	40 \pm 8

which were associated with a reduced number of days with growth (Table 3). At the annual scale, weekly precipitation and SWP often had a significant effect on weekly radial growth; the magnitude of these effects did not show a consistent increasing or decreasing trend over the 11-year period across five species (Figure 6).

4 | Discussion

Our findings reveal that elevated winter and spring temperatures led to earlier attainment of annual growth levels (i.e., 5%, 25%, 50%, and 75% of annual stem growth), indicating an earlier onset of tree growth driven by early season warming (Figure 1). Despite this advancement, the earlier start did not result in increased annual growth. On the contrary, total annual growth significantly declined in three species—*Abies alba*, *Fagus sylvatica*, and *Picea abies*—during the study period (Figures 2 and 3A). This decline in annual growth from 2012 to 2022 was accompanied by a reduction in the number of days with growth (Figure 3A) and a shift in growth sensitivity to temperature from a positive relationship to a negative one (Figure 6). Our results suggest that warming is constraining rather than promoting tree radial growth and contradicts the expectation that an earlier start of tree growth would increase annual growth because more days are available for carbon assimilation and radial expansion (Peñuelas and Filella 2001; Grossiord et al. 2022; Körner et al. 2023).

4.1 | Warming-Induced Advancement of Growth Onset and Its Impact on Annual Growth

The earlier achievement of annual growth levels is clearly associated with increased early-season temperatures, underscoring their role in advancing the onset of cambial activity. Warmer spring conditions are known to accelerate phenological processes such as budburst and leaf expansion, enabling earlier photosynthesis and growth initiation (Basler and Körner 2014). However, this early advantage was largely offset by subsequent

warm and dry conditions in summer (Figure 4) resulting in significantly negative annual growth trends in three of the five species (Figure 2). The observed reductions in growth appear to be driven more by environmental variability than by ontogenetic factors. This is supported by our finding that *F. sylvatica* and *P. abies* exhibited similarly negative growth trends across both large and small trees, with no significant size-related differences (Figure S4). These patterns are consistent with broader regional trends. Recently, Etzold et al. (2025) reported declining stand-level basal area growth for *A. alba*, *F. sylvatica*, and *P. abies* in Switzerland—the same species that showed significant declines in our study. Likewise, recent dendroecological studies across Europe have documented drought-induced reductions in radial growth in *F. sylvatica* (Martinez del Castillo et al. 2022; Klesse et al. 2024).

4.2 | Factors Constraining Tree Growth

In four of the five species, earlier growth onset was negatively correlated with total annual growth (Table 1), indicating a disconnect between phenological advancement and productivity gains. Several studies suggested that an earlier start of growth would not necessarily translate to greater stem growth; rather, stem growth is related to environmental conditions of the growth period that determine growth occurrence, maximum growth rate, and number of days with growth (e.g., Zweifel, Sterck, et al. 2021; Dow et al. 2022; Etzold et al. 2022; Matula et al. 2023).

Over the 11-year study period, Switzerland experienced at least four drought years (2015, 2018, 2019, and 2022) (Figure S6). These drought years reduced radial growth during the respective years, and additionally in subsequent years because of legacy effects (Kannenberget al. 2020; Zweifel et al. 2020; Braun et al. 2021; Tresch et al. 2023). The results we observed, such as shifts in growth phenology, dynamics, and total annual growth, are also observed for other species in northeastern North America (e.g., Dow et al. 2022). It is, hence, likely that

climate change (i.e., early season warming followed by warmer and drier summer) will cause significant changes in the yearly growing cycles in many temperate forests, limiting their growth and carbon sequestration in the future.

Our results show that although an earlier accomplishment of annual growth was related to winter and/or spring temperature (Figure 1), annual growth was not associated with the warming in winter or spring (Figure 3). These results could be seen as contrary to several tree ring-width-based studies where warming in winter and spring was often found to be positively related to annual growth (e.g., Bose et al. 2020; Harvey et al. 2020). The dendrometer-determined daily growth of wood and bark in combination with measurements of temperature, precipitation, VPD, and SWP provides greater temporal insight into which variable(s) drive(s) tree growth and at what magnitude (Zweifel, Sterck, et al. 2021). Our results show that annual growth was positively related to spring temperature at only five of the total 48 sites and was not related to the elevation of any other sites or species (Figure S5). The three tree species (*A. alba*, *F. sylvatica*, and *P. abies*) that displayed significantly decreasing trends of growth experienced increasing trends of winter and spring temperatures and a decreasing trend of summer SWP in the topsoil over the 11-year study period (Figure S7). The increased warming in winter/spring may increase respiration but also the water demand for growth and canopy development. In addition, a warm spring could be followed by a warm summer where the water demand for transpiration can lead to soil drought (Quesada et al. 2012). The enhanced water demand may induce physiological stress and associated radial growth decline under reduced SWP in summer (Gruber et al. 2010; Walthert et al. 2024). Thus, even if winter/spring warming causes an earlier start of tree growth, lack of water and increasing water demand under higher temperatures may modify the relationship between warming and tree growth. This might offset C gains associated with warming and an extension of the growing season (Richardson et al. 2013). In addition, increased warming and dry summers can reduce radial growth rate due to turgor limitation despite warmer temperatures generally being favorable for cambial activity (Peters et al. 2021).

Earlier growth onset may also expose trees to late spring frost events (Hufkens et al. 2012; Richardson et al. 2018; Zohner et al. 2020), leading to foliage loss and thus shortening the effective growing season length. Moreover, frost events can increase the requirement for additional carbon resources to produce new leaves (Augsburger 2009) that might require up to one-fourth of the tree's total carbon storage (Hoch et al. 2003). Together, such legacy effects of damaged foliage and the requirements for growing new foliage can significantly reduce a tree's annual growth (Vitasse et al. 2019; Bose et al. 2024).

Stem growth is not necessarily closely linked to carbon availability from actual photosynthesis, as there is always a delay between carbon uptake and carbon sink activity in a large organism like a tree (Cuny et al. 2015; Buttò et al. 2025), where resources need to be transported over days and weeks to reach their target tissue (Gessler and Zweifel 2024). Cell division and expansion (i.e., a central cellular prerequisite of stem growth) can cease under water- or temperature-limited conditions. Hence, warm conditions in late June or July may not result in tree growth if

water is not sufficiently available (Muller et al. 2011). Gessler and Zweifel (2024) suggested that optimality principles balance water and carbon resources utilization by trees to optimize growth in the long term. Such stomatal optimization of turgor-driven growth (Peters et al. 2021; Potkay and Feng 2023) provides a straightforward explanation of the importance of water relations for tree growth.

4.3 | Relative Importance of Environmental Factors in Intra-Annual Growth

Concerning the environmental factors driving weekly radial growth during the growth period, the results from our multi-model inferences suggest that temperature had the strongest (quadratic) effect, followed by precipitation irrespective of species (Table 2). The other variables, including day length, VPD, and topsoil SWP, also significantly impacted weekly growth, but the effect size was smaller compared to temperature and precipitation (Table 2). These results indicate that weekly temperature fluctuations are able to capture the intra-annual variabilities in stem radial growth in these temperate forests, which has also been reported in other studies (e.g., Cuny et al. 2015; Hinko-Najera et al. 2019). However, this weekly relationship of temperature to growth decreases with increasing temporal resolution of the comparison. Etzold et al. (2022) (daily resolution data) and Zweifel, Sterck, et al. (2021) (hourly resolution data) found both stronger explanatory weights of VPD and SWP than of temperature based on the same data source. This indicates that temperature serves as a good integrating indicator for growth due to its generally seasonal behavior on longer (weekly and longer) time scales, whereas moisture conditions in air (driving transpiration) and soil (providing water resources) are closely related to mechanisms explaining tree water relations and growth (Zweifel et al. 2001; Steppe et al. 2006). Furthermore, VPD and temperature are generally closely related (Grossiord et al. 2020). It is important to note that our SWP measurements were conducted in the topsoil layer (10–20 cm) only, which restricts our ability to assess water supply from deeper soil layers. Additionally, we lack data on rooting depth and subsurface soil structure, which are important for understanding SWP dynamics throughout the soil profile. In most of the forests studied, growth starts in spring and peaks in early summer when soil water availability is not yet a limiting factor (Etzold et al. 2022) and the evaporative demand of the air has been shown to be the most limiting factor for growth (Zweifel, Sterck, et al. 2021). Additionally, Switzerland has seen a more consistent rise in temperature over the past decades than many other parts of the world, while precipitation has remained largely unchanged nationwide (Figure S8).

As expected, the effect size of temperature on weekly radial growth started positively and peaked early in the growing season. However, the positive effect of temperature shifted to negative early (within 23rd week) especially for conifer species (*A. alba*, *P. abies*, and *P. sylvestris*) (Figure 4). Among the three conifers, *P. sylvestris* exhibited a stronger and more prolonged negative response, likely due to the geographic locations of the sites being relatively drier than those of the other species (Table S1). These three conifers are isohydric, exhibiting strong stomatal control that allows them to close their stomata early during the onset of the dry season. However, this strategy may compromise

growth (Peters et al. 2023; Walthert et al. 2024). This pattern of transition from positive to negative effects of temperature corresponds to the decreasing trend of weekly growth and maximum daily growth rate towards the later part of the growth period (Figure 5). In Mediterranean climates, hot and dry summers induce bimodal growth in many tree species (Campelo et al. 2021; Salomón and Camarero 2024), where growth begins in spring with earlywood formation, halts in summer, and may resume in late summer or autumn if rainfall and moderate temperatures return, leading to latewood formation (Camarero et al. 2010; Valeriano et al. 2023).

5 | Conclusion

The fact that warming advances the start of tree growth in spring but does not increase annual growth needs to be included in future projections of the carbon sequestration potential of forests. It is known that the increased frequency of summer drought events and heat waves to be expected in the future will jeopardize many forest functions, with reduced carbon sequestration being an important aspect. There was hope that an earlier start of the growing season could increase tree growth and thus more than compensate for heat- and drought-induced carbon losses. Our results for five of the most common tree species in central Europe refute such expectations.

Author Contributions

Arun K. Bose: conceptualization, formal analysis, methodology, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Sophia Etzold:** conceptualization, data curation, methodology, validation, writing – review and editing. **Katrin Meusburger:** data curation, funding acquisition, validation, writing – review and editing. **Arthur Gessler:** data curation, funding acquisition, methodology, validation, writing – review and editing. **Andri Baltensweiler:** funding acquisition, writing – review and editing. **Sabine Braun:** data curation, validation, writing – review and editing. **Nina Buchmann:** data curation, validation, writing – review and editing. **J. Julio Camarero:** validation, writing – review and editing. **Matthias Haeni:** formal analysis, writing – review and editing. **Ansgar Kahmen:** data curation, validation, writing – review and editing. **Richard L. Peters:** data curation, writing – review and editing. **Frank J. Sterck:** validation, writing – review and editing. **Simon Tresch:** data curation, investigation, writing – review and editing. **Lorenz Walthert:** data curation, validation, writing – review and editing. **Roman Zweifel:** conceptualization, data curation, funding acquisition, methodology, validation, writing – review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data and code that support the findings of this study are available from Dryad at <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.z8w9ghxrq>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.